

But my concern is whether Epicurus's argument gives us emotional comfort, or whether Epicurus' argument eliminates or weakens the fear of death. I've been thinking and worried about this issue in the past. Because Epicurus's argument is not giving me any comfort. For me, his argument is like this. Someone says to someone who is overweight.

"You have to eat only when you get greater happiness than when you don't eat Because your appetite is for happiness But because of your overeating, you are losing your long-term happiness. Your appetite is irrational! I completely proved that your appetite is irrational! My proof succeeds to eliminate your irrational appetite!"

If someone succeeds to eliminate his desire because of that, maybe he is definitely insane

My thoughts are composed of four things.

We have a tremendous desire to live.

Epicurus believes that this irrational desire can be eliminated by reasonable argument.

However, numerous desires, such as sexual desire, appetite, and sleep desire, do not seem to be "removable" only with reasonable argument.

If a reasonable argument cannot eliminate irrational desires, Epicurus' argument cannot eliminate the fear of death.

The biggest purposes of appetite is the survival and health of our bodies. So it's possible to take that advice and go on a diet. But our bodies are fundamentally designed for survival. We can say that the lives of black slaves were terrible and unhappy. But how would the black slave react when he sees a murderer trying to kill him? Will he shout, kill me? The answer is, "save me!" The reason is that the fundamental purpose of our body is to survive.

I guess Epicurus thinks like that, that if you tell children there is no monster under the bed, the fear of monster will disappear and The same is true of the fear of death.

However, the problem is that they misunderstand, the reason why we fear death is for survival. We have a very strong instinct for survival. And the purpose of this aspiration is to exist. We will do anything to live.

Therefore, we understand that there are people who cannibalized their colleagues when they were shipwrecked, and we even sympathize with them.

In fact, it may be debatable that there is a desire to survive. However, according to many psychologists and scientists, human survival instincts do not only exist but are also too powerful. Death psychology specialists (Sheldon Solomon, Jeff Greenberg, Tom Pyszczynski) wrote about survival instinct like this

"We may think we are afraid to die because our bodies will rot, stink, and turn to dust, because we will leave our loved ones behind, because we've left important things unaccomplished, or because we have the sneaking suspicion that no loving God awaits us, ready to enfold us in his arms. But underlying all these concerns is that fundamental biological imperative. As Juliane Koepcke and other survivors have discovered, we will do just about anything to stay alive." (on the pages 16 of the Worm at the Core) The reason why humans are afraid of death is because of the "survival instinct close to an obligation," and the fear of death is very powerful and it is the irrational but most powerful instinct of humans.

Professor Kwon Seok-man (권석만) (Seoul National University), a renowned psychology professor in Korea, also wrote in his academic book "The Psychology of Death," (삶을 위 한 죽음의 심리학) "There is an endless desire to live in humans, and the reason why we fear death is because of the instinctive desire of life to exist."

And suicide psychologist Joiner also mentioned the tremendous strength of human desire to live. "The fear of death is universal and virtually unshakeable. It is so powerful that it persists even in people who have suppressed it enough to drink horrible poisons like bichloride of mercury or hydrochloric acid, to jump off the Golden Gate Bridge, or to go over Niagara Falls. Therefore, it is a safe assumption that virtually everyone who desires death also simultaneously desires life. The suicidal mind is characterized by ambivalence, with competing forces tugging at the suicidal individual from the sides of both life and death." (Myths about Suicide, pp. 63-64)

Considering the testimony of these psychologists, it seems true that we have an unreasonable desire to exist endlessly.

This is the grounds for my second assumption.

For example, humans know that smoking will make their lives terrible and suffer tremendous pain. However, most people can't stop smoking. If this seems to be a special case, let's think of it. Our parents want their children to be happy. That's why They ask their children to study. However, as we know well, most of their children hate studying and waste their lives on useless games. Therefore, sometimes our educators play so-called motivation-promoting videos for students.

The content of the videos is simple." If you don't study, you'll do what you hate the most and your dreams will be ruined. You need enough time to overwhelm others to get into a good university, don't be confident that you're smart and think about the times you've wasted. If you had studied at that time, you could have achieved your dream." The video is a very rational and reasonable argument that succeeds in increasing students' desire to study and eliminating their desire to play. But comedy is like this. the lecturer says "Most students always will watch the video again in 10 minutes". This is because, obviously, they were completely persuaded by the video's claims (the irrationality of the desire to play and the enormous long-term happiness of studying) but their desire to play continues to haunt them. If we succeed in eliminating the desire to play with such persuasion, surely our educators will be able to make our children geniuses with little effort.

That's why the lecturer in the video keeps saying this. "The students don't study!" If a physiological and instinctive need is resolved by a reasonable argument, How comfortable would our lives be? We know so many foolish things we do, even if we agree perfectly with a number of rational reasons not to do, If not, why the majority of Americans are still overweight, and why are so many of our students wasting their time playing?

Is it because they give them more happiness than the future? If yes, why? Do we regret eating fast food while on a diet until we die? And why do we regret that we should have studied more when we get older? Shouldn't we react like this if they gave us more happiness than future happiness?

Professor sheldon Solomon, Jeff Greenberg, Tom Pyszczynski experts in death psychology, commented on Epicurus' claim.

"These are cogent arguments, worthy of serious consideration. However, Epicurean efforts to eliminate death anxiety on rational grounds have been spectacularly unsuccessful to date. People have not changed all that much in the last three thousand years; they remain steadfastly disinclined to die, and passionately devoted to acquiring literal and symbolic immortality." (worm at core.229)

This is a bit of a religious story, but Buddhism teaches that life is a series of suffering. They think that desire itself increases pain more and more, and the clergy of the religion are convinced of it in both "intellectual" and "emotional" aspects. However, in that religion, there is only one "Buddha" who has been officially freed from all desires. but Buddhist priests's Prostitution and corruption are often seen. And Buddhism considers liberation from desire as a divine stage. Buddhist monks are convinced that "unreasonable desires" are more painful and useless in terms of emotion and intelligence. So didn't they live single and reject all social pleasures? However, even those beings suffer from endless desires, and regard person who can eliminate the desires as a "divine being", only Shakyamuni is considered to be historical. If a reasonable Epicurus argument can succeed, why? Have Buddhist priests failed decisively, contrary to Epicurus' claim?

And most Buddhist priests believe that pure "intellectual" knowledge, contrary to Epicurus' argument, is impossible to eliminate desire. That's because it's not knowledge, it's wisdom.

If, as Epicurus argues, pure "knowledge" can eliminate desire, Why did this religion fail decisively to eliminate the desires?

And it will not explain why Buddhist priests can't get rid of irrational desires. They firmly believe that our desires are irrational and cause pain, but they have not yet

reached a state in which they do not pursue them.

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<https://www.matthieuricard.org/en/blog/posts/what-does-buddhism-mean-by-enlightenment>)

If Epicurus' argument had succeeded to eliminate the irrational desires through rational arguments, there would be at least tens of millions of Buddhas in Buddhism.

Is it because they are foolish intellectually? I am sure that even the lowest level of monks among

them will be able to make a complete and intelligent argument about the irrationality of the fear of death and the pursuit of desire. I can guarantee that their logic is a very reasonable argument, as Epicurus' argument, if the underlying assumption of their argument is correct. Although the argument may be wrong from the critic's point of view, isn't Epicurus' argument the same?

It's a very vulgar metaphor, but this argument is like this. Men have some complex about their penis. We feel some irrational and strong inferiority when our length and circumference are smaller than others.

In a way, we have a pathological longing for great genitalia. Scholars affirm that our sense of inferiority is irrational. They bring statistics that the size of the genitals has little to do with sexual satisfaction. Then they find our Achilles heel of this complex. However, if it were overcome by such a reasonable argument, I bet the sexual organs of the porn actors would have been small.

Ordinary men cry out "That's true. But I hope mine is bigger than my friend's!"

And can we call the state practical? Because even such noble priests have not reached!

My second assumption may not be clear. But if this assumption is wrong and Epicurus's argument is correct, we can eliminate the desire to play for only reasonable reasons, and we will succeed in dieting by eliminating irrational appetite for only reasonable reasons, and we will be able to escape the rule of our desires. However, we know very well that this is impossible. That's why we can never eliminate desire only for reasonable reasons. We never succeed to escape the rule of desire.

Because if my assumption is wrong, our world will be a very different world and full of unexplained things. Then the proponents of Epicurus could make this counterargument.

Some desires can be eliminated for reasonable reasons.

If Epicurus supporters make this argument, I will answer like this.

I think some desires can be eliminated, but the underlying desires cannot be eliminated like human instinctive animal desires. What if it would eliminate those desires, too? Why do we live suffering from such irrational desires? Why do we agonize between studying and entertainment? Also, why do we always fail to diet?

If anyone says that he was no anguish in dieting or studying for only reasonable reasons, he would be a psychotic or the worst liar.

No one can argue that only reasonable arguments can eliminate animal instinctive desires. Because it's a direct opposite to the experiences we've gained in our lives.

So it seems self-evident that we cannot eliminate our animal desires with reasonable reasons.

That's why death psychology Professor Solomon, said that Epicurus' argument was decisively unsuccessful. This is because he also agrees with this opinion.

If so, they can make this counterargument.

The desire to survive is not an animal or fundamental desire.

Therefore what is our most animalistic and most fundamental desire?

What is the most powerful desire? It seems so obvious that the desire to survive is such a desire. This argument is supported by the argument of Professor Solomon, the death psychologist.

As far as I know, it's almost common sense in biology that all living things have the instinct of self-preservation.

In fact, if this is not an animal desire, is it from the "noble" mind of our humans? Is it our social desire? Or is it a desire for self-realization?

How should we categorize this desire? What category should we categorize this desire into?

I think the most plausible category is animal physiological needs. This is because all other categories are not suitable for this at all.

The famous Maslow Need Hierarchy Theory also explains that the bottom needs are physiological needs, so the desire for the endless survival of "object" is the most primitive and animal needs.

Rational arguments often control desires, but the problem is that such control seems likely to become powerless according to the strength of desires. We can temporarily suppress appetite, temporarily suppress sleep, and temporarily suppress the desire to play. But did this suppression really get rid of desire? And we call people who quit smoking or drugs completely superhuman. I'm sure reasonable arguments have helped. But if that makes us quit smoking, the world will be really comfortable. What makes us quit smoking is mental strength as a result. Strong-willed people quit smoking. However, the issue seems to be that overcoming the fear of death is more difficult than quitting smoking. Because even very strong desires such as appetite and sleep desire are fundamentally an extension of the desire to survive, so we feel that it is disastrously difficult to overcome our survival instincts. For example, some people were wrecked, they run out of food and starved for three weeks, a reasonable person said, "Even if you eat one of us now, we only extend our lives a little and will you be happy to live in a shipwreck for a long time?" As you know, life on this shipwreck is hell, so let's not eat each other, let's starve to death like gentlemen," do you believe this reasonable argument will prevent cannibalism on a shipwreck??

Even suicides who gave up their lives are attached to life, and they are not free from it at all, and they love life fundamentally and have a tremendous will to live, as Professor Joiner wrote in his book, Myths about Suicide, even those suicides love their lives more than anyone else. Therefore, when they interviewed people who fell from the Golden Gate Bridge, most of them said they regretted it a lot after falling. They testified that

they had strong urge to live when they fell, and they recognize that they really want to live. As Professor Joiner said, suicides are, in some ways, just mortal beings who want to live in fear of death like us. Could we overcome the fear of death even those who have almost given up their lives are so afraid of death?

Professor Thomas Joiner, a psychologist, noted in his book Myths about suicide that it is almost impossible for a man in misery to commit suicide by only for reasonable reasons. He thinks humans must be crazy to commit suicide.

But this doesn't mean that they have hallucinations or abnormal delusions like schizophrenics. It means here is that they should have some kind of depression or psychological abnormality.

Humans do not commit suicide because they are unhappy. They commit suicide when they can't stand it.

It seems the same, but it's different. Some people choose to commit suicide if they have mental problems even if their lives are good.

A case in point is a girl in Singapore who committed suicide. Perhaps many people think that the reason she committed suicide was because of misfortune. However, her family was rich and did not abuse her. However, reading her diary revealed that her motive for suicide was not "objective unhappiness" in life.

according to her diary, her pessimism about her life and poor school score were the causes of her suicide.

She didn't think her life would be "seriously" unhappy because of this. But she decided to die because her poor score was an attack on her own "self-image" and made her look like a shabby person so that she seemed to be an unnecessary nobody.

Her suicide was truly tragic and heartbreaking, but objectively irrational. She grew up in a wealthy family, and most of her worries were close to adolescent delusions. If any low-income children sees her, they will feel her like a serious idiot.

But her suicide came as no surprise to suicide psychologists (Suicidal: Why We Kill Ourselves by Jesse Bering 116~145).

Her suicide explains why many rich children and celebrities commit unreasonable suicide.

And it also helps explain why many people in objective misery do not commit suicide.

Suicide psychologists argue that humans die because of psychological pain, not physical pain.

Professor Shneidman, an authority on suicide psychology, argues: "The main purpose of my discussion of physical pain is This is to ensure that the kind of pain that belongs to the body is not the kind of pain that causes suicide The pain that leads us to suicide now is related to psychological pain or mental

pain." (The Suicidal Mind KOREAN VERSION 32~33)

This means that the cause of human suicide has little to do with "objective physical happiness." Humans do not commit suicide because of objective suffering.

If so, we can predict that most Jews committed suicide in Ayushwitz, but surprisingly, the fact that Ayushwitz's suicide rate was remarkably low.

What is the reason? The reason for this is that the lack of a sense of belonging and a sense of uselessness are the fundamental drivers of suicide.

(It's compellingly pragmatic advice. More than that, however, it's supported by empirical evidence. When we feel needed, we're less likely to take our lives. This may help us to understand the counter-intuitive but well-known finding that suicide rates tend to plummet during wartime, when there's a shift in the cultural focus away from individual differences and toward the unification of in-group members. A similar precipitous drop in America's suicide rates occurred in the immediate aftermath of events such as John F. Kennedy's assassination, the Challenger space shuttle explosion, and the 9/11 attacks.

This effect of group cohesion has even been used to explain why the suicide rate was lower than one would expect among those imprisoned in concentration camps during the Holocaust)(Suicidal: Why We Kill Ourselves by Jesse Bering 79)

If suicides are killed because of reasonable unhappiness and happiness, there is no explanation for these behaviors of Ayushwitz Jews and the decrease in suicide rates in emergencies.

Professor Thomas Joiner, an authority on suicide, also expresses his views on rational suicide in his book.

This is what he argues about the cause of suicide.

"my view is that the vast majority of deaths by suicide, approaching 100 percent, involve a combination of learned fearlessness with two simultaneous, long-lasting states of mind: 1) the view that one burdens others to such a degree that one's death will be worth more than one's life; and 2) the view that one is profoundly alienated from others. It is difficult if not impossible to hold these states of mind and to be 'rational' in the sense that most people mean when they use the term 'rational suicide.'" (Myths about Suicide, p. 188)

He said he believes that the cause of suicide is not a matter of reasonable pain, but of psychological pain, so it is the result of an unreasonable mind.

He also argued that the most selfish psychopaths, such as the "Cleckley Psychopaths," do not commit suicide, but only commit deceptive suicide, even if they do not want to die for their own benefit.

"In a data set of 330 individuals who were suicidal at the time of assessment, we searched for those who endorsed an index of suicidal intent at high levels, but endorsed an index of suicidal desire at low levels. Sure enough, ten individuals displayed this profile, around 2.5 percent of the total sample of suicidal individuals.

Having affirmed that these individuals exist, we next wanted to characterize them on an array of personality and clinical variables. We compared this group to other individuals on the array of variables, and the mystery was solved—the group who intended suicide but did not desire it obtained high scores on measures of narcissism and antisocial personality features. These individuals were likely 'Cleckley psychopaths' who actually did intend suicidal behavior without desire . . . in order to run some sort of con on others, much as the 'suicide is painless' hedge-fund fraud did. This is precisely the pattern of results that Cleckley would have predicted—'Cleckley psychopaths' never engage in suicidal behavior unless it is intended to manipulate or deceive others (e.g., to deflect attention from their crimes; to get out of responsibility)." (Myths about Suicide, pp. 50-52)

The fact that psychopaths did not desire suicide means that they had no intention of dying, and that they tried to commit suicide because they wanted to deceive people. If they don't intend to use people, they won't try to commit suicide.

This seems to be against common sense. If people commit suicide when they fall into

misfortune, so if they commit suicide for their own happiness, shouldn't those selfish psychopaths have a higher suicide rate than the public, and they should desire suicide more and more?

It is increasingly denied that the purpose of suicide is to escape from one's selfish objective suffering. It is contradictory that psychopaths have little intention of committing suicide if suicide is to promote their selfish objective happiness.

The reason why people commit suicide is deeply related to the reputation of others, such as mental pain and self-esteem. Therefore, it is related to their self-image. They die when they feel they are a burden and when they feel useless, so they die because of mental pain. They don't die by objective pain like rational reason.

In other words, people commit suicide only when self-esteem and self-image are destroyed and the ability to inflict fatal injuries on themselves is combined. Professor Joiner described these as 1. Feeling that oneself is useless 2. A sense of alienation from others.

This argument can answer, "Why do not North Koreans commit suicide?". Suicide psychologists think that humans die because of subjective mental pain, not objective pleasure.

It could be explained that why most of the suicides were in a wealthy state in the past.

"One of the more surprising things about suicide is that most people who kill themselves have actually lived better-than-average lives. When we get a little too accustomed to uneventful and pleasant conditions, warns Roy, a sudden, precipitous drop in our standard of living can dangerously disorient us. It's the law of social gravity: Compared to the guy who's been living his whole life down there, hitting rock bottom is going to hurt a lot more for the person taking a tumble off the side of a mountain. We're all downwardly mobile to some extent, but it's the magnitude of the discrepancy between our personal standards and our current life situation that plays a role in the presuicidal process. An experience that to many of us wouldn't seem so bad, or at least certainly not something to end one's life over, to others makes for an unlivable existence. This is because that individual has unrealistic—or unsustainable—criteria for their success."(Suicidal: Why We Kill Ourselves by Jesse Bering104)

"Roy amassed a mountain of epidemiological data to support the claim that suicidal thinking is precipitated by events that fall short of high standards and expectations.* Sometimes, as in Vickerman's case, these expectations are owed to our own past achievements, but they can also be the result of what Roy refers to as "chronically favorable circumstances." Simply being poor isn't a risk factor for suicide. But going suddenly from relative prosperity to poverty is. Likewise, being a lifelong single person isn't a risk factor, but the abrupt shift from being married to being single places one at significant risk of suicide. Most suicides in jails and mental hospitals occur within the first month of confinement, during the person's initial adjustment to this sterile new existence.

Dealing with unreasonable or impossible external demands can be our downfall as well. When others place their trust in us in ways that are overwhelming, the fear of letting them down can be crushing. This may be one reason why students who take their own lives often have a glowing record of academic achievement and parents with high expectations, but in the semester preceding their suicides, their grades fall."

(105,106 Suicidal: Why We Kill Ourselves by Jesse Bering)

Simply being poor is not the cause of suicide. This is because suicide occurs when they are in a situation that does not meet their own subjective standards. Paradoxically, if they were seriously unhappy from the beginning, those people would not commit suicide for only the reason.

In fact, as Epicurus' supporters think, if suicide is caused by objective happiness, why are North Koreans exploited and starved now? Why they do not commit to suicide? They are truly at the extreme of misery.

Suicide psychologists also believe that humans should lose their minds when committing suicide. They believe that they must have at least a little mental illness.

Psychologist Bering describes the state of suicides, explaining Professor baumeister's six-step theory of suicide psychology.

[The most important point to stress with regards to this fourth step is that the majority of suicides are driven by a need to escape from immense and ongoing negative affect (that aptly named "psychache," if you recall). They do not follow a cool-headed stream

of Socratic dialogue. A suicidal person doesn't idly contemplate "to be, or not to be," nor do they ask, as someone once falsely accused Camus of writing, "Should I kill myself, or have a cup of coffee?" When someone you care about is in this state, trying to use reason and logic with them can be as useful as advising a person with a compound fracture of the leg to just walk it off, or telling a schizophrenic patient that it's all just in their head.

For the truly suicidal, consciousness is incapacitating.](Suicidal: Why We Kill Ourselves by Jesse Bering108)

[As a result of being in a cognitively deconstructed state, these barriers collapse one by one. The suicidal individual's capacity for meaningful thought is impaired; with a drone-like focus on concrete details, abstract thinking that would normally generate spiritual or other protective ideas about, say, finding hidden purpose in suffering are alarmingly absent. Shneidman once remarked that "the single most dangerous word in all of suicidology is the four-letter word only." Those who are intent on taking their lives, in other words, have entered a mode of dichotomous thinking characterized by all-or-nothing reasoning. The situation has become black-and-white; there's no metaphysical subtlety, only life-or-death.](Suicidal: Why We Kill Ourselves by Jesse Bering 112~113)

True suicides can not accept the rational Epicurus argument because they are too mentally challenged to think of philosophical problems. They can only die if they are crazy.

That's why Professor Thomas Joiner also expressed a negative view of rational suicide. Humans do not die for reasonable reasons. At least most people choose suicide only when their minds are slightly damaged.

Professor Thomas Joiner affirms that all suicides are mental patients.

"The best evidence to date indicates that around 95 percent of those who die by suicide have a diagnosable mental disorder at the time of their death. Personally, I believe that is probably an underestimate, and that the figure is closer to 100 percent—I believe that, in the vast majority of cases, the 5 percent without clear mental disorders at the time of their death are experiencing subclinical variants of mental disorders."

(Myths about Suicide, p. 89)

Although not all suicides have a severe mental illness such as schizophrenia. Professor Joiner argues that they are somewhat crazy.

If suicide is possible only when man is crazy, Epicurus' argument for the rationality of suicide is just an meaningless philosophical argument.

As psychologists argue, if rational suicide is impossible or extremely rare, Epicurus' argument will not be practical.

However, this fact may not be a big problem. This is because philosophical theories and scientific theories are meaningful even if they are impossible to practice. For example, we can't time travel, but in theory, time travel is meaningful to realize the great truth. However, the biggest problem with Epicurus' argument is that it is a "treatment" and a practical "recommendation." Epicurus' argument is designed to eliminate the fear of death or to free humans from the fear of death. So this argument is a kind of antidote.

Antidote should be effective. If it doesn't work, it's just a kind of pun with no value or meaning.

However, this does not deny the "logical" rationality of Epicurus' argument. However, this means a practical failure of Epicurus' argument.

However, no matter how many professional certificates prove the effectiveness of the medicine, if it is not effective for patients, it is the same medicine made in pseudo-science.

This is because the treatment is evaluated not as a logical or theoretical effect, but as a practical effect.

There are still numerous cancer medicines coming out, and they appeal that they are medicines through very reasonable and plausible arguments in their own way, but most of them are just fake medicines of no value because they are ineffective even though they have reasonable reasons. Therefore, I will address the final counter-argument. Were there not numerous Epicurean followers or those who claimed it was possible to accept death? However, if the logic of this paper is valid, I must concede that it compels the following conclusions: 1. They are all liars. 2. They are self-deceiving. 3. They have genuinely transcended biology (this suggests to us that they have transcended biology or are perfect freaks). And I am compelled to consider them as one of these three conclusions, because this is the conclusion that this paper forces.

To all the scholars and people who claim to have eliminated their fear of death by rationally proving that death need not be feared I grant three options: 1. You are a liar. 2. You are a self-deceiver. 3. You have performed a miracle. The prominent scholars who supported this argument—David Hume, Spinoza, Russell, are caught in the preceding dilemma if this thesis is true.

Furthermore, the so-called 'noble' literature, films, and all works of art that support this (the tale of the third brother in Harry Potter's Deathly Hallows, the movie Puss in Boots: The Last Wish, and almost all other secular works that accept death) are also reduced to being either lies, self-deception, or fantasies that demand a miracle.

Therefore, my opinion is that Epicurus' argument cannot help us.

In summary, my argument is that even if we prove perfectly logical that we don't need to pursue desire, that desire will not disappear.

It has already been proven by our experience.

I don't think rational arguments can get rid of this fear of death.

The fear of death can only be overcome by eliminating the desire of life. I wonder what you think.
I wish you have a nice day